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Machine Learning Applied to High Entropy Alloys under Irradiation

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High-entropy alloys (HEAs) represent a frontier in materials science, offering many promising features suitable for high-demand applications in nuclear and space sectors, such as exceptional mechanical properties. However, a major challenge in these fields is accurately predicting the behavior of HEAs under extreme conditions, such as radiation exposure or elevated operating temperatures, in order to maintain the integrity of the materials. Machine learning (ML) provides powerful tools to address this challenge. ML techniques, including ML interatomic potentials (MLIP), enable the modeling and prediction of complex behaviors in HEAs. This review focuses on ML to enhance the understanding of phase stability, mechanical properties, and radiation damage prediction in these complex alloys. The potential of ML to accelerate the discovery/optimization of new HEA compositions with good performance under extreme conditions is also discussed. Ultimately, the aim is to highlight the transformative role of ML in the field of HEAs under extreme conditions, in light of developing novel materials suitable for harsh environments.

1. Introduction

1.1. High-Entropy Alloys (HEAs) for Challenging Environments

The design of materials that can withstand extreme conditions is a pressing challenge in fields such as nuclear energy, aerospace, and space exploration. Extreme environments are characterized by high levels of irradiation, or elevated temperatures, which can dramatically decrease the structural integrity and performance of materials.

For instance, this will be crucial for the structural materials used in the next generation of advanced nuclear energy systems, such as Gen-IV nuclear fission reactors and nuclear fusion reactors, due to the need to resist higher temperatures, more severe

corrosion, and increased neutron irradiation compared to Gen-II and Gen-III nuclear fission reactors.^[1,2]

Currently, various materials are being investigated as potential candidates for structural applications in Gen-IV nuclear fission reactors and nuclear fusion reactors.^[3,4] However, each material presents specific limitations, including irradiation embrittlement at low damage levels (≈ 10 dpa), susceptibility to irradiation-induced hardening, low toughness, or a high concentration of highly activated elements.^[3,4] In principle, certain HEAs have the potential to mitigate these challenges.^[5] HEAs exhibit exceptional mechanical properties, enhanced thermal stability, and superior resistance to radiation-induced damage, making them attractive for use in extreme environments. HEAs represent a paradigm shift with respect to the conventional alloy design strategy. Contrary to traditional alloys, HEAs are made up of several elements—at least five—in nearly the same composition, usually being equiatomic. The key factor that emerged in HEAs is the richness in composition, which corresponds to having additional degrees of freedom in terms of elements, e.g., Mn, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, and Cu. This strategy, in stark contrast to the traditional alloying method, allows an incredible amount of combinatorial possibilities of compositions, thus opening the horizon to a variety of new materials with novel properties. The exceptional properties of HEAs are primarily attributed to four core effects: high mixing entropy, which stabilizes the solid-solution phase; lattice distortion, which enhances strength and resistance to deformation; sluggish diffusion, which improves thermal stability; and the

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cocktail effect, which results from the synergistic interactions among multiple elements. These effects contribute to HEAs' ability to maintain structural integrity under extreme conditions, making them highly attractive for next-generation reactor applications. HEAs are characterized by their high mixing entropy, which plays a crucial role in phase stability. This entropy is mathematically expressed as $S_{id} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{\alpha} c_{\alpha} \log c_{\alpha}$, where c_{α} is the concentration of element α and N is the number of atoms. The mixing entropy increases when multiple elements are present in nearly equal proportions, promoting the formation of stable solid solution phases. The solid solution phase in HEAs can exhibit various crystal structures, including face-centered cubic (FCC), body-centered cubic (BCC), hexagonal close-packed (HCP), or dual-phase combinations (e.g., FCC + BCC, FCC + HCP).^[6] Since crystal structure directly influences the mechanical properties and radiation response of HEAs, accurate phase prediction is essential. To predict phase formation, several semiempirical models have been developed based on physicochemical parameters, such as enthalpy of mixing, entropy of mixing, atomic size differences, valence electron concentration, melting points, and electronegativity mismatch.^[7] However, given the vast compositional space of HEAs, more sophisticated modeling approaches, coupled with high-quality datasets, are required for accurate prediction.

The combination of multiple principal elements in significant amounts creates a "cocktail effect," believed to enhance the interaction among all elements and provide opportunities to achieve new mechanical properties. For this reason, many works have been published in the literature and have led to the development of nonequiatomic HEAs, multiphase HEAs, metastable HEAs, HEAs with interstitial alloying elements, medium-entropy alloys (MEAs), and other variations that eventually have led to the broader family of complex concentrated alloys (CCAs). See **Figure 1** for the explosion of activity. The scientific community explored different strategies in alloy design with the aim of building materials with extraordinary mechanical properties. This, however, poses a challenge, as the large amount of data has made it difficult to conclude the mechanical predominance of HEAs

over "standard" alloys. This is particularly important if one considers only mechanical parameters. The two very important reviews on the topic of HEAs, by Miracle et al.,^[8] and George et al.,^[9] state that "Direct comparison of data is difficult, due to differences in the type and concentration of principal elements, the type and extent of thermo-mechanical processing, and the temperature and duration of post-process thermal treatment." This is even more important if we consider their radiation damage resistance. However, it is the key feature why these materials are better (or at least, for the time being, seem to show very promising properties in this regard) than usually used martensitic, austenitic steels, or Ni-based alloys. Therefore, one must always remember their additional exceptional feature, delayed damage build-up, when looking at their mechanical performance. For this reason, the quest for their chemical and microstructural optimization (mechanical properties are inherently connected to the microstructure of the material) should go on and this is one of the basic reasons to present this review.

One of the core effects of HEAs that strongly influences their mechanical properties is lattice distortion. In HEAs, each atom is typically surrounded by dissimilar atoms, and variations in atomic radii among different elements induce significant lattice strain. This distortion is more pronounced in HEAs compared to conventional alloys due to their multiprincipal element composition. A key parameter for quantifying lattice distortion is the atomic size difference (δ), expressed as:^[6]

$$\delta = \sqrt{\sum_i c_i \left(1 - \frac{r_i}{\bar{r}}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where the weighted average atomic radius is given by^[6]

$$\bar{r} = \sum_i c_i r_i \quad (2)$$

Here, c_i is the atomic fraction of element i , r_i is the atomic radius of element i , and \bar{r} is the weighted average atomic radius.

Figure 1. Trends in the number of articles on high entropy (or multicomponent) alloys and radiation over the last two decades. Data for 2024 is projected based on information available up to September 13, 2024. Source: Scopus.

A higher δ value indicates greater lattice distortion, which significantly hinders dislocation motion, leading to pronounced solid-solution strengthening.^[10] Solid solution strengthening (SSS) theory in HEAs establishes a strong correlation between δ and yield strength at room temperature. As δ increases, the yield stress also rises, reinforcing the idea that severe lattice distortion plays a crucial role in enhancing the mechanical strength of HEAs.^[10] To compare the mechanical properties of medium and high-entropy alloys (M/HEAs) with other materials, the tensile and compressive strengths at room temperature are presented in **Figure 2**. Figure 2a displays data for uniaxial tension, showing maximum strength versus total elongation, while Figure 2b presents uniaxial compression values versus compressive strain. In Figure 2, each symbol represents a specific phase or a phase mixture. First of all, the presented data indicates that HEAs (and/or CCAs) exhibit tensile strength or ductility that goes beyond those of classical structural alloys. The observed mechanical properties are within the parameters observed in classical or targeted applications of martensitic or advanced high-strength steels and nickel-based alloys. However, one should, of course, remember that one common feature for most of the HEAs is that they usually did not undergo extensive microstructural optimization studies (e.g., grain size refinement, fine-tuning of phase fractions, or morphologies). Therefore, one should expect that room for improvement still exists. Secondly, as shown in Figure 2a, HEAs are distributed across both the high-ductility, low-strength region (FCC phase) and the high-strength, low-ductility region (BCC phase). This observation is important since, in the beginning, low tensile ductility was common, and often only compressive properties were reported.

Speaking about compressive properties, at first glance, many of the verified HEAs display significantly improved compressive strength compared with conventional engineering alloys. Figure 2b clearly shows a different trend than the typical “banana curve” depicted in Figure 2a, describing the strength-to-ductility trade-off. In this case, most of the data lies within the ultimate compressive strength of 1000–3000 MPa and strain of

0.1–20%. Therefore, one may conclude that in this feature, HEAs outperform conventional materials. However, one must be aware that this particular parameter heavily depends on the experimental conditions: samples with a 2:1 ratio and deformed beyond 50% strain are constrained by the platens, strain should be below the buckling threshold, and finally, barreling due to friction between the sample and platen can artificially increase measured compressive strength. These cons in the compressive strength measurement cannot be the reason for the remarkable properties of $\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{CoCrFeNi}$.^[11] Joseph et al.^[11] reported that this HEA exhibits a compressive strain of 97% and compressive strength of 1378 MPa, which is attributed to the activation of mechanical twinning.

Since many alloy-design efforts aim to build materials for high-temperature applications, in the next step, we looked at temperature effects on the strength of HEAs and described the behavior of some of them in comparison to advanced Ni-based alloys. As mentioned earlier, mechanical properties are strongly dependent on crystal structure. BCC refractory HEAs (RHEAs), with their high melting temperatures, exhibit superior strength in compression tests up to 1600 °C, surpassing Ni-based superalloys.^[12] Their exceptionally high-temperature strength is attributed to edge dislocation motion, which is significantly hindered by energy barriers generated by random solute fields.^[13] Maresca and Curtin developed a robust analytical model to predict the yield strength of BCC RHEAs at high temperatures based on the energy barrier for edge dislocation motion.^[13] This model provides a predictive framework for designing high-strength BCC RHEAs for elevated-temperature applications, where lattice misfit and elastic modulus are key governing parameters. While BCC RHEAs exhibit superior mechanical properties at high temperatures, their limited ductility at room temperature remains a critical drawback for assembling these alloys.^[12] However, efforts have been made to improve ductility^[14,15] For instance, the introduction of ordered nanoprecipitate B2 phases in BCC RHEAs has been shown to enhance ductility.^[15] Such ordered phases can be formed through thermal annealing at specific

Figure 2. Comparison of mechanical properties of M/HEAs with various crystal structures and other well-known alloys at room temperature: a) tensile strength vs. elongation to fracture and b) compressive strength vs. compressive strain, as reported in ref. [9]. “2nd” and “3rd” AHSS refer to the second and third generations of advanced high-strength steels, “DP steels” refer to dual-phase steels, and “TRIP steels” refer to TRIP steels. Reproduced with permission.^[9] Copyright 2020, Elsevier.

temperatures.^[16] Density functional theory (DFT) combined with multicell Monte Carlo simulations offers a promising framework for predicting the formation of stable B2 phases in RHEAs.^[17]

In the case of FCC and dual-phase FCC-BCC HEAs, comparisons with Ni-based superalloys and stainless steels (**Figure 3**) reveal that tensile yield stress and ultimate tensile stress decrease as temperature rises. This phenomenon can be observed in the full range of temperatures. The drop is the highest in the low-temperature regime and becomes rather gentle from 300 to 800 K. After reaching a certain critical temperature limit, the drop again is more noticeable (which is also common for commercial counterparts). Regarding the 316 stainless steel and its tensile properties, they are essentially the same as equimolar CoCrFeMnNi and Cr-containing quaternary HEAs. This trend is maintained over the whole range of temperatures. INCOLOY 800 exhibits higher yield strength, while INCONEL 600 outperforms HEAs with FCC and dual-phase FCC-BCC structures in both yield strength and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) at high temperatures. However, further microstructural optimization could modify this trend, as most reported HEAs require refinement. A common challenge for FCC HEAs in high-temperature applications is their relatively low melting point. In Ni-based superalloys, the γ' phase plays a crucial role in maintaining high-temperature strength.^[18] One potential strategy for strengthening FCC HEAs is through the formation of ordered nanoprecipitates, such as the $L1_2$ (γ') phase.^[19] These nanoprecipitates hinder dislocation motion and enhance strength.^[19,20] By optimizing chemical composition and utilizing phase prediction tools, it is possible to stabilize these phases at high temperatures, thereby improving the mechanical performance of FCC HEAs in extreme environments.

For materials operating at high temperatures, fatigue is a critical form of mechanical degradation, particularly in aerospace and aero-engine applications, where components experience cyclic loading and unloading. M/HEAs not only exhibit high strength at elevated temperatures but also demonstrate excellent fatigue resistance.^[21,22] In M/HEAs, factors such as severe lattice distortion, ordered precipitates, chemical short-range order (CSRO), and modifiable stacking-fault energy (SFE) contribute to enhanced fatigue performance, including improved fatigue strength and resistance to fatigue crack initiation.^[15,23,24] In conclusion, HEAs provide a unique advantage as they offer a vast compositional space in which the different deformation

mechanisms may be tuned and optimized very effectively via their chemical modification (with more degrees of freedom). This results in the development of new alloys with superior properties, and it is particularly interesting for specific and narrow applications, like nuclear fission and fusion reactors, as well as aerospace.

Additionally, there is a growing interest in leveraging machine learning (ML) to enhance our understanding and optimization of HEAs. Traditional experimental methods alone are insufficient for fully understanding the complex behavior of HEAs. ML techniques can be exploited to utilize vast amounts of data to predict the behavior of these materials under various conditions, thereby accelerating the discovery of new alloys with desired properties. This is a general trend in materials science and the use of ML and sometimes interchangeably Material Informatics has exploded. The generic avenues of ML/MI application are reflected below in the HEA context.

1.2. Material Informatics and ML

ML interatomic potentials (MLIPs) and other ML methods provide powerful tools for modeling and predicting the phase stability, thermodynamic properties, mechanical behavior, and irradiation response of HEAs. By combining experimental data with ML predictions, researchers can gain deeper insights into the mechanisms governing HEA behavior and identify promising new compositions more efficiently.

This review covers several aspects of HEAs related to ML and irradiation. We will explore how ML can enhance our understanding of the thermodynamic and mechanical properties of HEAs under irradiation, with a specific focus on MLIP and ML techniques for predicting mechanical properties. To illustrate the growing interest in this field, we have above presented a typical plot showing the number of research articles published per year on HEAs, and irradiation (Figure 1).

Next, we summarize for the reader the main directions of ML in metal alloy research, of which HEAs are an example. The applications of ML in this field follow the main lines of materials research assisted or guided by this tool.^[25–33] Of particular interest are the acceleration of material development; the optimization of compositions and processing methods as well as the use of large language models (LLMs) may become important soon.^[34]

Figure 3. Tensile data of 3d transition metal CCAs: a) yield strength and b) ultimate strength vs. temperature. Data for three commercial solid-solution, austenitic alloys are shown for comparison: 316 stainless steel, INCONEL 600, and INCOLOY 800.^[8] Reproduced with permission.^[8] Copyright 2017, Elsevier.

1.2.1. Material Design and Discovery

ML models can predict the properties^[33] (e.g., elasticity,^[35–38] strength, corrosion resistance, thermal conductivity) of an alloy based on its composition. Instead of conducting expensive and time-consuming physical experiments for every potential combination of metals and other alloying elements, ML algorithms can provide quick predictions that narrow down the most promising materials.^[34,39] This approach leads to two main issues: how far ML predictions remain viable beyond the training data and the human-centered interpretation of the results (e.g., why this composition). In particular, high-throughput screening exploits ML to analyze large datasets from computational materials science or, more rarely, from experiments. The hope is to quickly identify new alloy compositions that could exhibit desirable properties, without resorting to combinatorial experiments. Here and in the case of “small data” as with so-called Bayesian or GPR approaches, we see the potential problems of data reliability and incompleteness. The latter is seen often in composition landscape analysis, where existing data leave gaps and lead to the idea of surrogate data creation, e.g., using generative adversarial networks (GANs).

1.2.2. Optimization of Alloy Composition

These approaches can be divided into two categories: a forward approach of composition tuning, where existing data on metal alloys are exploited by ML algorithms to optimize the composition of an alloy in order to achieve specific properties, such as increased strength or improved ductility under phase stability constraints.^[40] This optimization can involve tuning elements in small amounts or proposing novel combinations that were previously unconsidered. The second category is the Inverse Design paradigm, in which ML models (often GANs) are used to reverse-engineer the desired properties in terms of an ideal composition of an alloy. Below, we discuss a case in which Bayesian optimization (BO) is used to search for variants of the Cantor alloy with higher yield strength.

1.2.3. Prediction of Microstructure Evolution or Process-Structure-Property Relationships

We might make a distinction in using ML as a predictive tool for the microstructure-property relationship or using it in the more complex context of processing conditions that change. For alloys, the evolution of the structure (grain size and phase distribution) is a key for the final properties, and it may be grasped with ML methods. A more ambitious approach is to use ML to mimic material synthesis or processing from casting to additive manufacturing. The promise of this idea is again avoiding actual testing.

1.2.4. Accelerating Material Development and Characterization

Not far from the previous approach, ML can be introduced in experimental^[41] or computational or mixed workflows to help to grasp complicated data or indeed guide the process^[42] as in the case of self-driving laboratories or so-called Materials Acceleration Platforms. A conceptually easy application for ML is borrowing methods from computer vision and image

recognition to microscopy (SEM and TEM). There, it is used for post-processing and (semiautomatic) feature recognition, for example, in identifying grain structures, defects, and dislocations. These approaches are used to automate the analysis of materials during characterization.

1.2.5. Alloy Modeling

ML approaches currently serve in two main roles: providing substitute fast approaches such as molecular dynamics (MD) potentials for complex alloys or in some cases even substituting for simulations altogether by, for example, using DFT to accumulate datasets that are then used for creating ML models. Again, one of the main advantages is the savings in computer time when trustworthy ML models allow exploration of complex composition landscapes. Another example is the prediction of mesoscopic alloy properties using, e.g., the finite element method (FEM) to generate datasets that relate mechanical properties—such as stress-strain behavior—to microstructural features. These datasets are then used in ML models for property prediction and optimization.

1.2.6. Big Data, Materials Databases, and Material Informatics

Data mining and database creation are recurrent topics, particularly in the context of managing material simulation and property data at the atomistic level. Several initiatives—such as the Materials Project, the AFLOW database, and the NOMAD project—have emerged in this context, combining repositories of materials data with analysis tools, increasingly incorporating ML. For advanced alloys, the CALPHAD software remains a key resource for phase stability prediction and, in certain cases, property prediction. In the case of HEAs, the existing toolset is still limited due to the enormous complexity of alloy composition and property space. Nevertheless, ongoing work in materials informatics continues to pave the way for improved data curation and handling for future applications.

When selecting compositions from the vast array of possible elements to formulate M/HEAs for nuclear applications, several criteria are considered. For in-core applications, elements with low neutron capture cross-sections are prioritized, along with those exhibiting low gamma activities over both short- and long-term cooling periods. This element selection process is guided by computational methods.^[43,44] While nuclear-specific properties are critical, it is equally important to select elements that ensure good phase stability across various temperatures and excellent mechanical performance. ML models utilizing the physicochemical parameters of HEAs have demonstrated the ability to predict phase formation and stability,^[45,46] aiding in the selection of compositions with high-temperature stability. The demand for HEAs with superior mechanical properties for structural applications in the nuclear industry—such as high strength, ductility, fracture toughness, corrosion resistance, and irradiation resistance—necessitates the optimization of elemental compositions. ML, trained on both experimental and simulation datasets, plays a crucial role in designing and optimizing HEA compositions. By incorporating fundamental concepts such as the

four core effects, ML accelerates the discovery of novel alloys with outstanding mechanical performance.

Displacement damage and nuclear transmutation reactions are two significant types of damage mechanisms affecting metallic alloys used as structural materials in nuclear facilities.^[47] Displacement damage occurs when a target atom is displaced from its original lattice site due to neutron collision. Depending on the energy of the incident neutron, this can lead to a displacement cascade. As the cascade cools, point defects (vacancies and interstitials) and defect clusters can form. The evolution and accumulation of these defects can lead to the degradation of the alloy's microstructure and properties. Typical manifestations of material degradation resulting from displacement damage include irradiation-induced embrittlement, hardening, swelling, segregation, and phase transformation.^[48–54] Transmutation reactions convert atomic nuclei into different elements or isotopes through neutron-induced reactions like (n, α) and (n, p) .^[47] These reactions produce new isotopes, helium nuclei, and occasionally protons or additional neutrons. As neutron fluence increases, these products accumulate within the material. Helium, in particular, tends to migrate and coalesce at grain boundaries (GBs), forming helium bubbles. This aggregation can induce swelling and embrittlement.^[55] ML not only enhances the understanding of key mechanisms in the radiation response of HEAs (e.g., through MLIP) but also enables the prediction of radiation-resistant compositions by training on experimental and simulation data from HEAs exposed to irradiation with varying compositions.

1.3. HEAs and Radiation Damage

Structural materials for future nuclear reactors must not only possess good mechanical properties and corrosion resistance but also exhibit low activation—minimizing long-lived radioactive isotopes after irradiation—and high radiation resistance. Radiation-resistant HEAs can be developed by effectively limiting defect production and inhibiting their accumulation. Additionally, they should have the capability to immobilize vacancies at service temperatures and accommodate helium and hydrogen without degrading mechanical properties.^[56] M/HEAs exhibit excellent radiation resistance. For example, FCC HEAs display fewer defects after irradiation up to a certain dose compared to Ni and binary alloys, as confirmed by both computational and experimental results.^[57,58] Several reasons have been proposed to explain the radiation resistance of M/HEAs. Studies have demonstrated that this resistance originates from a reduction in defects generated during the primary damage stage.^[59–61] This reduction is attributed to the enhanced thermal spike and low thermal conductivity of HEAs, which results in higher efficiency of defect recombination. Another reason for the radiation resistance and swelling resistance of M/HEAs is related to their distinct defect diffusion kinetics. The characteristic high mixing entropy, chemical disorder, and lattice distortion in these alloys increase the migration energy of radiation-induced interstitial atomic clusters.^[62] This alteration modifies the diffusion behavior of these clusters, transitioning from 1D long-range movement to 3D short-range diffusion^[58] (see **Figure 4**). The transition to 3D short-range

Figure 4. a) Schematic illustration of 1D motion in nickel and NiCo. Interstitial clusters migrated fast along the glide cylinder. b) Schematic sketch of defect evolution and distribution in nickel and NiCo as a result of a. c) MD simulation result of the trajectory of the center of a four-interstitial cluster in NiFe showing a 3D migration mode. d) Schematic sketch of defect evolution and distribution in NiFe, NiCoFe, NiCoFeCr, and NiCoFeCrMn as a result of c. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License from ref. [58]. Copyright 2016, Springer Nature.

diffusion of interstitial clusters enhances interstitial-vacancy recombination, thereby reducing the number of surviving point defects and suppressing swelling.^[58,63] Figure 4 illustrates the different defect accumulation mechanisms in alloys with 1D diffusion (e.g., Ni and Ni-Co, Figure 4a) compared to those with 3D diffusion (e.g., NiFe, NiCoFe, NiCoFeCr, and NiCoFeCrMn, Figure 4c).^[58] As schematically shown in Figure 4a,b, in materials with 1D interstitial diffusion, such as Ni, interstitial clusters migrate along the glide cylinder without efficiently encountering vacancies, leading to vacancy supersaturation and an increased risk of void formation. In contrast, as illustrated in Figure 4d, in alloys like NiCoFeCr, interstitial clusters and loops act as vacancy sinks due to their 3D diffusion, reducing vacancy concentration in the matrix and effectively suppressing void formation and swelling.

Helium bubble swelling and embrittlement can be mitigated in HEAs. Vacancies (V_{vac}) and helium clusters demonstrate high binding energy, leading to the formation of $V_{m,vac}He_n$ bubbles during helium irradiation or nuclear transmutation reactions. Severe lattice distortion and chemical disorder in HEAs trap vacancies and irradiated helium atoms, preventing the aggregation of helium bubbles.^[64–68] Additionally, internal stress fluctuations in HEAs can slow helium atom diffusion and helium bubble movement.^[64]

FCC M/HEAs have received significant attention for fission nuclear power applications, while BCC HEAs are being considered as candidates for structural materials in fusion nuclear power plants. Although extensive research has been conducted on the radiation response of FCC HEAs, low-activation M/HEAs are of particular interest for nuclear environments. Examples of such alloys whose irradiation responses have been tested include equimolar CrFeMnNi, $Cr_{19}Fe_{31}Mn_{11}Ni_{39}$, $Cr_{20}Fe_{35}Mn_{25}Ni_{20}$, $Cr_{23}Fe_{26}Mn_{19}Ni_{32}$, $Cr_{15}Fe_{35}Mn_{15}Ni_{35}$, CrFeMnNi-ODS, $Fe_{50}Mn_{30}Co_{10}Cr_{10}/Cu$, $Fe_{38}Mn_{40}Ni_{11}Al_4Cr_7$, $Fe_{38}Mn_{40}Ni_{11}Al_4Cr_7Co_{2.1}$, $(Cr_{10}Fe_{30}Mn_{30}Ni_{30})_{94}Ti_2Al_4$, $Fe_{37.06}Ni_{30.47}Mn_{12.44}Cr_{12.00}Al_{4.01}Ti_{4.0}$, $Cr_{20}Fe_{32}Ni_{35}Mo_3Al_7Nb_3$, and $Fe_{33.7}Cr_{33.7}Ni_{32.5}$.^[69–79] While these alloys generally exhibit good radiation resistance, some perform better than conventional stainless steel. For instance, equimolar CrFeMnNi HEA irradiated with argon ions at room temperature to damage levels between 0.3 and 10 displacements per atom (dpa) showed less damage than the FCC phase conventional alloy SS316.^[73] Additionally, extensive research has been conducted on M/HEAs containing elements with high activation potential (e.g., Co-based M/HEAs) due to their excellent mechanical properties and radiation resistance.^[63,80–85] For example, NiCoFeCrCu_{0.12} HEAs, which contain Cu-nanoprecipitates, exhibited outstanding void swelling resistance and negligible radiation-induced hardening upon irradiation up to high radiation doses (i.e., over 100 dpa).^[84]

Developing advanced materials that can withstand the extreme environment of nuclear fusion reactors is a key challenge for achieving sustainable fusion energy.^[86] Plasma-facing materials (PFMs) are directly exposed to high-temperature plasma and must endure severe thermal loads, intense particle fluxes, and high-energy neutron irradiation. Additionally, they must resist helium and hydrogen implantation while maintaining long-term structural stability. While tungsten (W) is widely regarded as the leading PFM for fusion reactors, helium bubble formation under irradiation compromises its long-term structural integrity.^[87]

To address this limitation, HEAs have recently emerged as promising alternatives for such extreme environments.^[88–91] In this regard, many studies have investigated the radiation response of W-based, V-based, and W-V-based M/HEAs, demonstrating their good radiation resistance.^[88–97] Some of them showed even better radiation resistance than pure V or W. For example, the TiVNbTa HEA shows significantly less irradiation-induced hardening (0.66 GPa, 8%) compared to pure vanadium (1.19 GPa, 37%) at 3.6 dpa and 500 °C.^[92] A recent study by El-Atwani et al.^[88] introduced a refractory low-activation bcc $W_{38}Ta_{35}Cr_{16}V_{11}$ HEA that shows improved radiation resistance, with no irradiation-induced dislocation loops observed at room temperature and 1073 K up to 8 dpa. Another example is the MoNbTaTiW HEA, which demonstrated superior radiation resistance compared to W.^[89] Despite many studies devoted to designing novel alloys with good radiation resistance for nuclear applications, there remains a vast array of compositions whose radiation responses have not yet been investigated either experimentally or computationally. In summary, the radiation tolerance of M/HEAs is influenced by factors such as crystal structure, chemical composition, and the degree of atomic ordering. Certain M/HEAs exhibit superior radiation resistance, phase stability, and the ability to accommodate hydrogen and helium compared to traditional alloys and metals. The key challenge lies in identifying HEAs that maintain stability at higher temperatures and irradiation doses, particularly in helium- and hydrogen-rich environments.

1.4. Challenges in Predicting HEA Properties under Extreme Conditions

ML has developed as an important way of moving forward both integrated computational materials engineering (ICME) in silico and understanding experiments. ML has been increasingly applied in nuclear materials research.^[98] One important way to consider this development is to look at the multiscale modeling paradigm. ML serves in atomistic-scale workflows, particularly in the development of user-friendly interatomic potentials for simulating physical and chemical properties, following training on data derived from DFT.

Another important aspect for HEA understanding due to the complexity of the compositional landscape is to assist computational research and to summarize existing experimental research. This is used both for phase prediction and for property prediction or material design. As regards HEAs under extreme conditions, this work is still in its infancy compared to general progress. For irradiation-related issues like material tolerance or compositional design, the problem lies in the lack of material data across the range of irradiation doses. On the other hand, the modelling of such effects is taking steps forward due to the advances in MLIP research.

Aspects that need more research are the evolution of defect populations utilizing ML in order to surpass obstacles in spatial and temporal resolution, the common problem with atomistic level modelling. An underestimated avenue is the exploitation of these methods on larger-scale physics including simulations of irradiation effects.

The article is organized as follows. The first section discusses the role of MLIPs in enhancing our understanding of HEAs

through computer simulations, accurately describing a broader configurational space. We will also detail all MLIP developments for HEAs to date. In the subsequent sections, we will explore the role of ML in predicting the properties of HEAs to understand and mitigate radiation-induced damage, ensuring structural integrity under radiation exposure. Section 3 addresses the important question of phase formation and stability in HEAs in terms of a ML viewpoint. ML enables the prediction of mechanical and thermal properties of HEAs, which are crucial for enhancing radiation resistance. Predicting thermal properties, such as lattice thermal conductivity, aids in efficient heat management, preventing thermal degradation and maintaining performance in radiation environments. Similarly, ML allows for accurate predictions of mechanical properties such as tensile strength, yield strength, and elastic modulus. The discussion on the role of ML in predicting mechanical properties is presented in Section 4. These predictions facilitate the design of HEAs with superior mechanical and thermal stability, tailored for challenging radiation conditions. The next section of the article details predictions related to radiation resistance itself (Section 5). Finally, we provide an outlook on the subject, mentioning in particular long-term nuclear materials research efforts.

2. Challenges of MLIPs for HEAs

Atomic-scale simulations are efficient tools used to understand and predict material properties *in silico*. Those methods, like *ab initio* or MD, use different approaches to describe interatomic interactions. Therefore, those methods can give insight into the material from different perspectives, but each of them is limited to their length and time scales.

Until recently, it was a common puzzle to choose between the accuracy of *ab initio* and the efficiency of traditional MD/Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. However, the current trend is to bridge those two worlds by developing MLIPs. In this method, the interaction between particles is quantified by quantum-mechanical calculations (usually DFT), which are later processed in a machine-learning framework.^[99,100] Later, those potentials are used as an input to the larger-scale atomic-scale simulations. In such a way, the near-*ab initio* accuracy can be combined with time and length scales achievable by classical (CIPs) or semiclassical interatomic potentials (SCIPs).

While the technical details can vary, the MLIPs development process keeps a similar scheme^[100] visualized in **Figure 5**. Firstly,

one needs to have the output from first-principles calculations. Later, structure descriptors are used to pass the representation of this input dataset, to the regression model. The regression algorithm establishes the correlation between the structure features and properties, e.g., energy and forces. When local structure descriptors are used, the summation is done over those specific environments (usually over each atom's neighborhood), counting the contribution of each to the total system energy (locality approximation).^[100]

2.1. MLIPs

This architecture makes MLIPs more flexible than CIPs or SCIPs. There is no connection to physical equations. Therefore, MLIPs are not material-specific, and one can systematically improve them,^[100–102] by adding structures to train the dataset or retraining the model. Here, the most popular descriptors and regression models will be briefly introduced to the reader. More information on that matter can be found in refs. [99,100,103–106].

The information passed through the structure descriptors consists of atomic positions and energy of the structure, but sometimes also forces and virials.^[106] To unambiguously describe local atomic structures, the descriptors' output must be invariant to translation and rotation of the system, as well as to atomic permutation.^[103] A few of the most popular descriptors are as follows: smooth overlap of atomic positions (SOAP),^[107] bispectrum of the neighbor density,^[108] atomic cluster expansion (ACE),^[109] atom-centered symmetry functions,^[110] and moment tensor descriptors.^[111] Apart from such descriptors with a fixed form, descriptors can also be learned within the ML framework (learned descriptors).^[112] Regarding the regression models, some of the most popular are as follows: artificial neural network (ANN),^[113] Gaussian approximation potential (GAP)^[108] and other kernel methods, spectral neighbor analysis potential (SNAP),^[114] and moment tensor potential (MTP).^[111]

The descriptors and regression modes can be used in various combinations. However, the most suitable choice is not obvious, even if only for HEA applications. Depending on the objective, some methods have been shown to be better than others.^[115–117] For instance, Gubaev et al.^[115] demonstrated that both MTP and the Gaussian moment neural network (GM-NN), applied to the Ta–V–Cr–W alloy family, provide DFT-level accuracy, with MTPs offering faster convergence and GM-NNs achieving faster

Figure 5. General workflow for MLIP development for HEAs. The DFT output is mathematically represented by the structure descriptors. Later, the ML regression algorithms fit this structure-property data to create the force field (MLIP).

execution times. In practice, the choice often depends on the researcher's knowledge, preferences, or the availability of software packages in which specific MLIP tools are already implemented.

Despite the advantages of MLIPs over CIPs or SCIPs, current MLIPs have a few drawbacks. Firstly, MLIPs behavior is very dependent on the quality and design of a training dataset. Interpolation can be done well by current MLIPs, but they can be very misleading while operating in regions outside the training dataset. For example, MLIP trained on bulk structures may perform poorly in surface features investigation. Moreover, the extrapolation issue may affect mechanical property prediction, for extreme loads if the model was not informed with such strained structures.^[118] To add, the presence of defects in the training database might play a crucial role in accurate mechanical property or phase stability prediction.^[119,120] Modeling the latter is also more complicated in the case of multicomponent systems, for which the phase diagrams are not fully known yet. The challenge is to provide the training dataset with structures that are thermodynamically stable in a given temperature and pressure. Otherwise, MLIP can fail to predict some phases that are present in the real materials. To end, current MLIPs lack transferability between different systems since the developed models can be applied only to the systems they were trained for.^[104] In summary, current MLIP models designed for one objective should be validated before applying them elsewhere. One of the emerging methods used to overcome MLIP's transferability issues is to utilize general-purpose models and retrain them with new structures typical for desired applications. The successful application of this strategy can decrease the cost specific MLIPs development, while maintaining their accuracy.^[121]

Current MLIPs are also facing a few computational challenges. Firstly, the representation of magnetic properties is still at its infancy. The first attempts to incorporate magnetism effects are reported in the literature (e.g.,^[122–124]). However, most of the MLIPs are nonmagnetic, and incorporation of this phenomenon into the multicomponent systems is still a challenging task. To add, special care should be taken when developing MLIPs based on structures from different calculation procedures. Mixing of such input databases may lead, e.g., to failure in phase prediction.^[125] Similarly, despite the flexibility of MLIP architecture, designing an MLIP informed with interactions of very different bond characters might be difficult. For example, the DFT calculations of corrosion and formation of oxides require other theoretical approaches, e.g., hybrid functionals or Hubbard correction.^[126] Those methods are different than the standard exchange-correlation functionals used for purely metallic systems. Therefore, the creation of a consistent DFT database might be challenging in such cases. Moreover, the current MLIP descriptors often lack explicit long-range interaction terms (e.g.,^[103,127]), which might be important in the context of thermodynamic or mechanical properties prediction.^[128,129] Lastly, uncertainty estimation of the MLIP results is still a challenging task. Nonetheless, the number of methods aiming to develop even better MLIPs is constantly growing, as well as their application in HEA studies. The further sections will describe how MLIPs can be used to predict multiple properties essential for HEAs working in extreme conditions.

2.2. MLIPs for HEAs

The integration of MLIPs in atomistic simulations has markedly enhanced our ability to predict the mechanical properties of HEAs. By utilizing these advanced potentials, researchers can simulate large systems over longer timeframes, providing a detailed picture of how these materials behave under stress, deformation, or other mechanical loads. Specific case studies, such as the investigation into the vacancy energetics and migration in HEAs, have demonstrated the power of MLIPs to reveal intricate details about material behavior that were previously inaccessible.

Among the most widely used ML potentials for HEAs and multicomponent alloys are MTPs.^[115,130–134] These have been used to examine a range of properties, including thermodynamics, elasticity, and dislocation mobility in various HEAs.^[115,130–134] Other potentials, such as SNAP, tabulated GAP (tabGAP), deep learning (DL)-based potentials, and ANN potentials, have also been used to investigate elastic properties, atomic segregation, point defects, and mechanical characteristics under diverse conditions.^[90,135–140] For instance, research by Byggmästar et al. utilized MLIPs developed from first principles to study defects and segregation in RHEAs, providing insights into the complex interactions at play under various conditions, including high temperatures and mechanical stress.^[137] Another study highlighted the use of MLIPs to capture and predict the behavior of short-range order in HEAs, enhancing our understanding of phase stability and mechanical properties under real-world application scenarios.^[141] For even more examples of MLIPs application to HEAs study, the reader is referred to the refs. [142,143] and refs. therein.

It is important to reiterate that the effectiveness of MLIPs varies significantly depending on the quality and structure of their training datasets. Some MLIPs are tailored for specific alloy compositions, while others span a broader range. Additionally, certain MLIPs focus on accurately reproducing a single material property, whereas others aim to compute multiple properties accurately. The training dataset is crucial in the development of MLIPs. For instance, creating MLIPs for studying HEAs under irradiation requires generating a diverse and comprehensive training dataset. This dataset should contain a wide range of compositions, structure optimizations, calculations under applied strains, and ab initio MD simulations for both crystal and liquid phases and include various point defects and defect clusters.^[144] This comprehensive approach ensures the MLIP is robust, accurate, and capable of describing the complex microstructures of irradiated HEAs.

We will explore how MLIPs have been used to predict mechanical properties and radiation damage in Sections 4.1.1, 5.1.2, and 5.1.3.

3. ML-Based Prediction of Phase Formation in HEAs

HEAs are a quintessential class of compositionally complex alloys. They can obtain different structures with variable multiple-element compositions.^[145] By fine-tuning the phase structure of HEAs, different excellent property combinations can be obtained.^[146,147] However, the prediction of phase formation in HEAs remains one of the major challenges in this field. In

previous studies, several semiempirical methods have been proposed to predict the phase formation of HEAs.^[148,149] Despite the advances in the field of phase formation prediction, such process remains time-consuming. The march of Moore's law has driven advanced computing power, which enables ML-based predictions in complex systems, e.g., phase formation predictions of HEAs.^[150]

3.1. ML Models to Predict Phase Formation

A large number of ML algorithms have been applied to predict the phase formation of HEAs,^[151–154] e.g., ANN, decision tree (DT), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), naive (NB), generalized linear regression (GLR), random forest (RF), k-nearest neighbors (kNN), support vector machines (SVM), and residual network (RESNET). In Islam's work,^[151] a neural network (NN) in the ML framework was used for recognizing the data pattern. The trained NN parameters suggest that the valence electron concentration plays the most dominant role in determining the phase formation rules. For the cross validation training and testing datasets, a high generalization accuracy is obtained. The trained NN model can be extended to classify different phases in numerous other HEAs. In Huang's work,^[152] three different ML algorithms are shown: KNN, SVM, and ANN. The trained ANN model is the best one among these three algorithms. It is useful for predicting the phases of new HEAs. This work is also applicable to the development of other advanced metallic materials for applications. In Machaka's work,^[153] a framework is proposed that incorporates of 6 feature selection schemes, construction of feature ensembles, and 8 general ML classifiers, i.e., DT, LDA, NB, GLR, RF, kNN, and SVM. They were trained to evaluate the stability of the solid solution phase in HEAs. In Zhu's work,^[154] a RESNET-DNN is proposed for the phase formation prediction of HEAs. The model demonstrates high overall accuracy. Compared to conventional DNN and ANN models, the Micro-F1 score highlights its advantages in HEA phase prediction. The architecture helps prevent network degradation and improves predictive accuracy. Obviously, more newly developed ML algorithms can promote the development of the field of predicting HEA phase formation. In addition, the connection between computational science and materials science is crucial. One of the important issues in this field is to improve the interpretability in materials science of results obtained using ML.

3.2. Applications of HEA Phase Formation Prediction

HEAs have attracted great attention for laser additive manufacturing, due to their outstanding mechanical properties. However, their industrial application was hindered by high entry costs and the limited compositional library of HEAs. In most ML algorithms used to predict the properties of HEAs, their processing paths are not clearly distinguished. In Zhu's work,^[150] a novel deep NN (DNN) architecture was proposed that includes HEA manufacturing routes as input features. The manufacturing routes, as-cast and laser additive manufactured samples, are transformed into the One-Hot encoder. This makes the samples with different phase structures in the dataset provide better directivity and reduces the prediction error of the model. This work

delivers a new strategy to discover specific compositions that are suitable for laser additive manufactured HEAs. Interestingly, the phase formation of HEAs prepared by specific processes has been predicted using ML. In Ren's work,^[155] an ensemble ML approach is presented, which enables the discovery of sputtered single-phase solid solution HEAs by directly predicting quinary phase diagrams based on atomic composition. Using 2198 experimental data points from quinary HEAs, a RF classifier with bagging achieves 94.6% accuracy. The model predicts 224 quinary phase diagrams, covering $\approx 32\,000$ single-phase solid solution HEAs in the Cr–Co–Fe–Ni–Mn–Cu–Al system. First-principle DFT calculations validate the prediction capability of the model. Analysis of the model's input weights identifies valence electron concentration, work function, atomic radius difference, and elemental symmetries as key factors in HEA phase formation. In addition to the common predictions for single solid solution HEAs, there are also predictions for HEAs of solid solution plus intermetallic compounds. Krishna's work^[156] highlights the research interest in HEAs with multiple phase due to their promising properties and tunable microstructures. Using ML, a multiphase alloy system with solid solution and intermetallic phases from a dataset of 636 alloys is proposed. Algorithms applied included logistic regression (LR), DT, SVM, RF, Gradient Boosting (GBoost), and ANN, with ANN achieving the highest accuracy of over 80%. Experimental verification confirmed that ANN predictions were the most accurate among them. Notably, there is some work devoted to providing plausible physical explanations for ML results. For example, Lee's work^[157] utilizes a ML method for optimization, generation, and explanation to identify key design parameters in HEA phase prediction. Regularized DNNs are established to predict HEA phases, with optimization of hyperparameters related to model architecture, training, and regularization. The work explores the contributions of design parameters in identifying the solid solution phase.

Existing progress has revealed the important role and research potential of ML in the prediction of HEA phase formation. On the one hand, more newly developed ML algorithms can be applied to HEA phase formation prediction. On another hand, ML methods can interact more deeply with results obtained from DFT,^[145] MC,^[158] MD,^[159] and other methods. This will enable ML studies to obtain more detailed phase structure information, such as CSRO. In addition, in phase structure prediction research, the physical interpretation of ML results is crucial. This can build a bridge between computational simulations and metallurgical theory.

4. Mechanical Properties Prediction

The prediction of mechanical properties such as tensile strength, yield strength, hardness, and elastic modulus is vital for understanding and mitigating the impact of radiation-induced damage on HEAs. ML models have proven effective in accurately predicting these properties, thereby supporting the design of HEAs tailored for extreme environments. The quality and availability of training datasets are critical to ML performance, with data sources including experimental measurements, simulations, or a combination of both.

In cases where sufficient literature exists, automated literature mining—leveraging natural language processing (NLP) techniques—offers an efficient approach for extracting and compiling relevant data to guide HEA design. For example, Han et al. recently proposed an integrated DL–NLP framework to accelerate the discovery of high-hardness multicomponent HEAs.^[160] Their method analyzed 2698 publications from the past 5 years, extracting 8067 data points. By integrating NLP-based data extraction with materials domain knowledge, they constructed a comprehensive dataset and implemented a two-stage optimization strategy to design HEAs with enhanced hardness.^[160]

In the absence of extensive experimental datasets, ML models can be effectively trained using data from DFT calculations or MD simulations that use accurate interatomic potentials, enabling the prediction of mechanical properties and the design of HEAs with optimized mechanical behavior.^[161,162]

Atomistic simulations represent a breakthrough in materials science, as they allow us to understand the mechanisms that govern the behavior of materials at the atomic level, spanning scales inaccessible to many experimental methods. These simulations are also critical in the field of HEAs to understand and predict their mechanical properties. For example, numerical simulations have shown how HEAs can maintain structural stability and mechanical performance under irradiation.^[137]

However, traditional computational approaches, while robust, many times fail to capture the full complexity of HEAs because of their inherent compositional and configurational disorder. In addition, the scale at which traditional simulations operate may not adequately represent crucial multiscale phenomena in HEAs, necessitating advances in multiscale modeling techniques to bridge the gap between atomistic and macroscopic scales. This limitation underscores the need to improve existing simulation techniques. The recent advent of ML tools improves prediction accuracy and computational efficiency. One of the major advances in this area is the development of MLIPs. These potentials are designed to capture the unique and complex behaviors of HEAs at the atomic level, which traditional potentials often struggle to model accurately.

4.1. Predicting Mechanical Properties in Simulations

The role of ML in predicting mechanical properties through simulations is increasingly important. In this section, we discuss how ML, particularly in the form of MLIPs, can enhance the accuracy of atomistic simulations for predicting mechanical properties. Additionally, we explore how ML methods can be utilized to predict mechanical properties by using datasets generated through atomistic simulations.

In Section 4.1.1, we focus on the significant role of MD simulations in providing valuable insights into the mechanical properties of materials. Specifically, we address how MD simulations can be used to study material strengthening mechanism and the effects of irradiation-induced defects on mechanical properties through defect-dislocation interactions and nanoindentation tests. MD simulations are powerful tools for exploring atomic-scale interactions, but their accuracy heavily depends on the interatomic potentials used. The introduction of MLIPs has greatly improved the predictive accuracy of these simulations,

enabling more reliable results. Then, in Section 4.1.2, we review recent studies that have integrated MD simulations with ML techniques to identify optimal compositions of M/HEAs that offer specific mechanical properties. This approach is particularly valuable for navigating the complex, high-dimensional composition space of M/HEAs, facilitating the discovery of materials with optimized mechanical properties for a wide range of applications

4.1.1. Atomistic Simulations and the Role of MLIPs in Predicting Mechanical Properties

Atomic-scale computer simulations play a critical role in the multiscale modeling approach for materials science.^[163] These simulations offer researchers powerful tools to gain deep insights into the microscopic mechanisms underlying processes in materials while simultaneously providing quantitative data to inform mesoscale and continuum models. MD simulations can span length scales from individual atoms to ≈ 100 nm and cover time-scales reaching up to 100 ns. These constraints limit the use of MD simulations for materials under deformation, such as shear and stretching, to high strain rate scenarios. Beyond multiscale modeling, MD simulations can capture various strengthening mechanisms and phenomena that contribute to the mechanical properties of M/HEAs. MD can elucidate nanotwin strengthening,^[164,165] nanoprecipitate strengthening mechanisms,^[20,166,167] and SSS, enabling the development of complex alloys with enhanced strength.^[168,169] Additionally, the hardness of M/HEAs can be measured using MD simulations with a spherical indenter.^[158] Nanoindentation is a typical test conducted after irradiation to investigate its effect on hardness. In MD, if the microstructure can be accurately modeled post-irradiation, a nanoindentation test can be useful for predicting the mechanical properties of materials. This type of test is particularly valuable for assessing the effects of radiation on the mechanical properties of M/HEAs.

Since the accuracy of MD simulations depends on the quality of interatomic potentials, MLIPs can significantly improve simulation results. This improvement will be useful for designing novel M/HEAs with good mechanical properties and radiation resistance based on strengthening and radiation response concepts. Understanding the complex interactions between dislocations and obstacles such as nanotwins, nanoprecipitates, solute atoms, and radiation-induced defects through MD simulations is essential for uncovering the fundamental strengthening mechanisms that influence the mechanical properties of materials. SSS is a crucial factor in the design of strong M/HEAs. While the Varvenne-Curtin model is available for predicting this form of strengthening,^[110] it encounters limitations when copper is incorporated into FCC M/HEAs and aluminum into BCC M/HEAs. Additionally, a comprehensive model to predict strengthening in ordered M/HEAs is still lacking.

MD simulations offer valuable insights into these strengthening mechanisms by calculating the depinning stress of dislocations in M/HEAs. For instance, research by Esfandiarpour et al. has shown that in several FCC M/HEAs, increased lattice distortion correlates with higher depinning stress, leading to enhanced material strength.^[168,169] Nanoprecipitate strengthening can also be effectively analyzed using MD simulations. A recent study has

shown that the SFE mismatch between $L1_2$ nanoprecipitates and the matrix enhances material strength through dislocation–precipitate interactions.^[20] Additionally, CSRO and clustering of nickel atoms in CoNiCr alloys have been found to increase the depinning stress, thereby contributing to overall strengthening.^[166,167] Furthermore, the interaction between dislocations and nanotwins can be explored through atomistic simulations.^[165] Applying deformation to M/HEAs can reveal the transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP) effect, although these simulations often involve high strain rates.^[170] Understanding the interaction of dislocations with radiation-induced defects such as voids also contributes to our knowledge of the mechanical properties of M/HEAs under irradiation.^[171,172]

Advancing MLIPs can significantly improve the accuracy of predicting the mechanical properties of HEAs. It was demonstrated how short-range order affects the mechanical properties of NbMoTaW RHEA using several MLIPs.^[135,136] Additionally, generalized stacking fault energies (GSFE) and Peierls stresses for both edge and screw dislocations in BCC refractory metals have been calculated using SNAP, further highlighting the potential of MLIPs in advancing our understanding of material behaviors at the atomic level.^[173] Wu et al. showed that the formation of stacking faults and dislocation cross-slips in CrFeCoNiPd HEAs under uniaxial compression using an MLIP for CrFeCoNiPd is consistent with experimental observation.^[174] Mori et al. developed an MLIP to describe the interaction between dislocations and voids in bcc iron, showcasing another important application of MLIPs in modeling complex material behaviors under irradiation.^[175] Li et al. investigated the behavior of the CrCoNi MEA under nanoindentation both experimentally and through MD simulations using a NN potential (NNP). The MD simulations accurately explained the formation of the first pop-in load observed in the experiments.^[176]

In summary, atomistic simulations, particularly those using MLIPs, are crucial for exploring the complex mechanical behaviors of HEAs. These simulations not only provide insights into dislocation interactions and strengthening mechanisms but also build a platform for designing advanced alloys with improved mechanical properties. As MLIP development continues to progress, it is likely that the predictive capabilities of these

simulations will further improve, offering even more accurate and reliable predictions of material behavior. Future research should continue to integrate MLIPs with MD simulations to refine our understanding of HEAs and to explore new approaches to material innovation.

4.1.2. Leveraging Datasets from Atomistic Simulations and ML to Predict Mechanical Properties across Various Compositions of M/HEAs

To find an optimal composition of M/HEA (“composition search”) that provides specific mechanical properties, the combination of MD simulations and ML has been the focus of numerous studies.^[177–185] In this context, mechanical properties such as Young’s modulus, shear modulus, yield stress, flow stress, and critical resolved shear stress can serve as target properties for optimization across a vast composition space. MD simulations can generate a dataset of these properties for various compositions, and ML methods can then be applied to train on this data and identify the optimal composition. The various concentrations of three or more elements define a high-dimensional search space for M/HEAs. This can involve searching for non-equimolar M/HEAs that provide optimal mechanical properties. In the following, we refer to some of these studies.

Zhang et al. created a database describing the relationship between elemental composition and yield stress based on tensile tests on 300 single-crystal nonequiatomic Fe–Cr–Ni–Co–Mn HEAs using MD simulations.^[177] They demonstrated that a DNN model shows higher accuracy in predictions. The accuracy of the DNN model was further verified using polycrystalline HEA samples, where the prediction of yield stress was consistent with the MD simulation results.^[177]

In another study, a yield-strength-predictive ML framework was developed, consisting of five main processes: data collection, feature pool construction, model and feature combination screening, adaptive alloy design, and validation using MD simulations, as shown in **Figure 6**. This framework was used to find the nonequiatomic V–Cr–Fe–Co–Ni HEAs with high yield strength.^[185] The results showed that by using valence electron

Figure 6. ML framework for identifying nonequiatomic V–Cr–Fe–Co–Ni HEAs with high yield strength.^[185] This yield strength–oriented ML framework consists of five main processes, including a) data collection, b) feature pool construction, c) model and feature combination screening, d–f) adaptive alloy design, and g) validation using MD simulations. The green boxes indicate where the MD method was used, while the blue boxes indicate where ML was used. Reproduced with permission.^[185] Copyright 2023, Elsevier.

concentration, vacancy formation energy, and mismatch in cohesive energy as input features, a support vector regression (SVR) model with a radial basis function kernel represented the best-performing approach among numerous combinations of ML models and material features.^[185]

Elgack et al. investigated the prediction of tensile properties, including Young's modulus, yield strength, and UTS, for FeNiCrCoCu HEAs using MD and ML algorithms by considering a set of input parameters, including atomic concentrations, grain size, and operating temperature.^[179] They showed that ANNs provided the best accuracy in comparison with SVM and Gaussian process regression (GPR) models.^[179]

Recent studies have used BO to find compositions with optimal mechanical properties for Fe–Cr–Ni–Co–Mn and AlVCrFeCoNiMo alloys.^[178,184] BO is an active learning technique designed to efficiently identify optimal values of objective functions, particularly when these functions lack an analytical form and require point-wise evaluations of the target space through costly and time-intensive experiments or simulations.^[178,184] Using this approach, Torsti et al., starting from the equiatomic Cantor composition, discovered Fe₆Cr₂₂Mn₅Co₃₂Ni₃₅ after 72 iterations, achieving a 74% improvement in yield stress (see **Figure 7**).^[178] This result highlights the effectiveness of BO in accelerating the discovery of high-performance alloy compositions.

These studies highlight the powerful synergy between MD simulations and ML techniques in predicting the mechanical properties of M/HEAs. By using large datasets generated from atomistic simulations, ML models can effectively navigate the high-dimensional composition space to identify optimal alloy compositions with targeted mechanical properties. This

approach facilitates the discovery of compositions that meet specific mechanical requirements for various applications, including those that must withstand irradiation.

4.2. Predicting Mechanical Properties from Experimental Data

ML techniques have been developed and applied to various experimental data sets of HEAs to design alloys with desired mechanical properties.^[101,186–191] The ML methods used for predicting mechanical properties are regression based. In contrast, for phase identification, the methods are classification algorithms. Catal et al. utilized ANN, SVR, and RF models on the data sets of RHEAs to predict the strength, hardness, and ductility of new compositions and obtain compositions with optimal mechanical properties.^[186] This work details an alloy design effort by ML attempting to design novel RHEAs with exceptional mechanical properties at elevated temperatures and good room temperature ductility. For this purpose, four datasets were generated by mining the data available in the literature, containing room-temperature strength/ductility, high-temperature strength, and hardness, which were trained by three different ML models, namely the SVR, RF regression (RFR), and ANN. As a result, three novel RHEA compositions were predicted, and their performances were experimentally validated. Specifically, the Ti₈Nb₂₁Zr₂₇Ta₁₃Mo₁₉V₁₂, Ti₁₀Nb₁₉Zr₁₅Ta₄₃Mo₇V₆, and Ti₁₀Nb₂₀Zr₃₇Mo₂₁V₁₂ RHEAs were produced and subjected to room-temperature and high-temperature compression and room-temperature hardness tests, which have demonstrated that especially the Ti₈Nb₂₁Zr₂₇Ta₁₃Mo₁₉V₁₂ and the Ti₁₀Nb₂₀Zr₃₇Mo₂₁V₁₂ RHEAs exhibit both high strength at elevated temperatures and good room-temperature ductility.

Figure 7. The mechanical properties of HEAs—here compositional variants of the famous Cantor alloy—can be tuned by design by changing the element proportions from the equiatomic starting point. a) Stress–strain curves showing the improvement of mechanical properties with increasing iterations and the identification of the optimal composition. b) The yield stress (τ_y), c) the shear modulus (G) as a function of the iteration number, and d) the composition used for each iteration. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).^[178] Copyright 2024, The Authors, published by AIP Publishing.

The study contributes to the literature by presenting three novel RHEAs and constitutes an encouraging example of efficient alloy design by ML for demanding applications.^[186]

Wen et al. described an accelerated material design strategy involving an iterative loop of ML and the design of experiments (DOE) to predict Al–Co–Cr–Cu–Fe–Ni HEA alloys with high hardness.^[187] The iterative loop used a surrogate model using the SVR ML model with a radial basis function-based kernel based on the chemical compositions to predict hardness and related uncertainties for various alloys. Then, a utility function was used for DOE to pick a candidate material with high hardness and higher uncertainty, such that the data produced from the experiments could be further utilized to train and improve the accuracy of the ML model. The work also used another iterative loop in which the ML model was trained from the chemical compositions and some highly correlated physical features. The work envisaged ten new alloy compositions with the highest hardness values ranging from 859 to 883 HV. The alloys were high in Al content (up to 47%) and low in Cu content (<5%).^[187]

Wen et al. used an approach containing feature construction and selection to predict SSS and designed HEAs with high SSS utilizing RFR, SVR, Kernel ridge regression (KRR), Gaussian process (GP), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Bayesian regularized NNs (BRNN) ML models.^[188] The study devised a simpler and more accurate SSS model to predict the strength of single-phase HEAs, in contrast to the physics-based models. The model formulated SSS in HEAs with the features indicating the least errors and greatest correlation as:^[188]

$$\Delta\sigma_{ss} = \xi \cdot Z \cdot G \cdot \delta X_r \quad (3)$$

where Z is a fitting parameter, ξ is the structure factor, G is the shear modulus of HEAs, and δX_r is the electronegativity mismatch among elements. Thus, the study demonstrated that the changes in electronegativity of the elements facilitate the charge interaction among the atoms in HEAs and improve the effects of SSS beyond the conventional elastic interactions between the solute atoms and dislocations. The model examined four HEA systems, AlCoCrFeNi, CoCrFeNiMn, HfNbTaTiZr, and MoNbTaWV, and predicted the composition ranges with maximum SSS. For example, the composition ranges for AlCoCrFeNi alloy to obtain maximum SSS are Al(1.6–3), Co(0.5–1.4), Cr(3.2–3.5), and Ni(3.1–3.5).^[188] Figure 8 shows pseudo-ternary phase diagrams of the four HEAs examined in the study, indicating the composition ranges with maximum SSS marked in a color code.^[188] The color bars in Figure 8 indicate the variation of $G \cdot \delta X_r$, which is proportional to the SSS.^[188]

Some studies predicted the mechanical properties of the HEAs based on ML approaches, especially for the cases of time- and cost-intensive experiments.^[101,189–193] Bhandari et al. used RF regressor-based methods to predict the yield strengths of HEAs at higher temperatures. The yield strengths were found to be 709 and 572 MPa for MoNbTaTiW and 929 and 520 MPa for HfMoNbTaTiZr at 800 and 1200 °C, respectively, consistent with the experimental findings.^[192] The method was also utilized to estimate the yield strengths at 1500 °C, and the values were 516 and 489 MPa for MoNbTaTiW and HfMoNbTaTiZr, respectively.^[192] Chang et al. utilized an ANN-based ML approach on nonequimolar AlCoCrFeMnNi alloys to identify the composition with the highest hardness.^[193] Since the data sets were limited to only 91, the method focused on general trends rather than accurate comparisons with the

Figure 8. Pseudo-ternary diagrams showing the chemical composition ranges with maximum SSS (proportional to $G \cdot \delta X_r$, (MPa)) for a) AlCoCrFeNi, b) CoCrFeNiMn, c) HfNbTaTiZr, and d) MoNbTaWV HEAs. The compositions are represented in RGB color code indicating $G \cdot \delta X_r$, (MPa), where G is the shear modulus and δX_r is the electronegativity mismatch amongst elements. Reproduced with permission.^[188] Copyright 2021, Elsevier.

experimental data. The work identified the ANN model with an architecture of one hidden layer of three nodes providing acceptable accuracy. The study also used a simulated annealing algorithm to identify candidate compositions with low risk and high hardness. The research demonstrated that Co, Cr, and Al play a dominant role in achieving high hardness values greater than 500 HV, compared to Fe, Mn, and Ni. The study predicted three new compositions: $\text{Al}_{30}\text{Co}_6\text{Cr}_{35}\text{Fe}_6\text{Mn}_{18}\text{Ni}_5$, $\text{Al}_{25.5}\text{Co}_9\text{Cr}_{35}\text{Fe}_{10}\text{Mn}_{15.5}\text{Ni}_5$, and $\text{Al}_{24}\text{Co}_{18}\text{Cr}_{35}\text{Fe}_{10}\text{Mn}_{7.5}\text{Ni}_{5.5}$ with a hardness of ≈ 670 HV. The alloys were also manufactured, and the hardness values were calculated to agree with the ML predictions due to the BCC structure of alloys with β phases.^[193] Li et al. constructed three ML-based models, the solid solution and BCC models to classify phases and the HV model to predict hardness. RF classification and RFR ML algorithms accurately identified the phases and estimated hardness, respectively.^[10] Thus, the study described an integrated ML-based strategy of material discovery and designed a low-activation single-phase BCC HEA, $\text{Fe}_{35}\text{Cr}_{30}\text{V}_{20}\text{Mn}_{10}\text{Ti}_5$, with an optimal hardness of $574.2 + 32.2$ HV.^[10] The alloy was further manufactured and hardness predictions were validated via the experimental values. The alloy also exhibited compressive yield strengths of 1307, 843, 410, and 30 MPa at 25, 600, 800, and 1000 °C, respectively, superior to the conventional RAFM steels for nuclear applications.^[10]

To overcome the uncertainties raised due to experimentation, most authors collected data on materials produced only by casting and arc-melting.^[101,189–193] This way, the uncertainty in the ML models related to manufacturing and processing of materials was minimized.

To summarize the section, materials design based on data is moving towards integrating data, including surrogate data, from several sources. This trend might be quite useful for understanding HEA mechanical properties in irradiation environments since actual experimental effort is tough. One of course faces perennial ML challenges in such integration, including data heterogeneity and model generalizability if one desires to extrapolate much beyond the range of property space used for ML training.

5. Predicting the Radiation Response of HEAs

One of the important damage mechanisms in nuclear structural materials is displacement damage caused by neutron collisions. When a neutron collides with an atom, it creates a primary knock-on atom (PKA), initiating a displacement cascade, wherein a series of atomic displacements occurs and generates a localized high temperature region referred to as the thermal spike. The thermal spike lasts for a very short duration, typically on the order of picoseconds. After the cascade cools, it leaves behind point defects such as interstitials and vacancies. Depending on the irradiation dose, this event happens numerous times. The formation and evolution of these defects can degrade the mechanical properties, leading to phenomena like swelling, hardening, embrittlement, and segregation at GBs. Significant segregation at the GBs under irradiation can alter the cohesive strengths of the GBs, thereby affecting the material's fracture toughness.

M/HEAs have exhibited promising radiation resistance.^[79,84,93,194–199] The extent of radiation damage in M/HEAs can be affected by their crystal structure and degree of atomic ordering. While the FCC M/HEAs have demonstrated good ductility, the inclusion of cobalt (Co) can improve their strength. However, the activation of Co under radiation makes it less desirable for nuclear applications. As a result, Co-free M/HEAs are of particular interest for these environments.^[77,79,194–196,200] Recent studies have indicated that the introduction of short-range order and the formation of nanoprecipitates can further enhance both the mechanical properties^[20,166,168,201,202] and radiation resistance of M/HEAs.^[84,203–205] These microstructural features appear to play a key role in improving the performance of these advanced alloys under extreme radiation conditions.

W-based HEAs are gaining significant attention as structural materials for fusion reactors. In fusion reactors, structural materials are exposed to 14 MeV high-energy neutron irradiation, leading to the production of large amounts of helium and hydrogen, in addition to displacement defects.^[206] The interactions between He, H, and these defects cause substantial swelling and hardening, impacting the materials' mechanical properties and overall structural stability.^[207] In addition, in fission reactors, helium atoms can be created in Ni-based alloys due to nuclear transmutation reactions caused by the interaction between neutrons and Ni atoms. These helium atoms easily precipitate as helium bubbles, which further degrade the mechanical performance of alloys in nuclear reactors. Consequently, the number of studies on helium bubble interactions with HEAs is increasing.^[66–68,208–217]

While comprehensive review articles have discussed the irradiation effects in HEAs^[49,218] and the high-temperature irradiation of HEAs,^[219] the following sections will address recent studies on this topic and explore how ML can help predict radiation damage in M/HEAs. This discussion is divided into two main sections: the first focuses on how ML can help predict radiation damage and defect evolution in atomistic scale simulations, and the second examines how ML can be used to predict radiation effects using experimental datasets.

5.1. ML to Predict Defect Properties and Radiation Response

5.1.1. Radiation Damage in M/HEAs: MD Simulations Using CIP

Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) is a powerful computational tool that can be used for investigating radiation displacement damage and thermal effects on microstructures in metallic alloys.^[220] HEAs are complex materials, and certain thermal treatments can increase their complexity, for example, by inducing segregation at GBs, the formation of ordered phases, and the formation of helium or hydrogen bubbles. This complexity can be tracked using hybrid MC/MD or MD simulations with LAMMPS (**Figure 9b**). Primary radiation damage,^[59–61] cascade overlap for estimating damage from low dose irradiation,^[53,79,221–223] and the interaction of displacement cascades with micro/nano structures^[224–227] such as GBs, nanoprecipitates, and bubbles can be investigated using MD (**Figure 9**).

At the atomistic scale, MD simulations are extensively used to describe the radiation behavior of M/HEAs. Since displacement

Figure 9. a) Displacement damage in a single-crystal HEA for a single event (top) and 950 cascade events (bottom). The dense areas indicate regions of damage, including interstitial clusters. b) The effect of thermal treatment on HEAs, showing atom segregation of green and yellow atoms to the GBs (top left shows the GB structure, and top right represents the annealed sample starting from a random distribution), nanoprecipitate formation in the single crystal (bottom left), with green and yellow atoms forming the precipitates, and helium bubble formation in a HEA, indicated by green atom clusters (bottom right). Displacement damage simulations can be applied to more complex microstructures, such as those shown in panel (b).

cascades occur on picosecond timescales, MD simulations can capture the primary radiation damage stage, which experimental techniques cannot directly observe. The energy and direction of PKA, determined by the colliding neutron energy, govern the number and types of defects that can form within the material. Although radiation damage is a multiscale process, it is believed that for HEAs, if certain compositions result in fewer defects during the primary stage for a given range of PKA energies and directions, such simulations can aid in narrowing down the selection of radiation-resistant compositions.^[59,60,228] Several studies have demonstrated that the origin of radiation resistance in M/HEAs stems from a reduction in defects generated during the primary damage stage.^[59–61] This reduction is attributed to the enhanced thermal spike and the low thermal conductivity of HEAs, which results in higher efficiency of defect recombination. A differing perspective was offered by Deluigi et al.,^[229] who, through primary radiation damage simulations on the equiatomic quinary FCC FeNiCrCoCu alloy, proposed that the observed radiation resistance may instead be related to longer-term defect evolution mechanisms, rather than reduced primary damage arising from chemical disorder.

Defect production and evolution in metals and alloys do not result from a single neutron-atom collision but depend on the neutron irradiation dose. Cascade overlap simulation is a technique to investigate material irradiation up to several dpa. In these MD simulations, multiple cascade events are introduced into the simulation box at certain intervals. This approach has been used to compare the radiation response of HEAs and MEAs up to several dpa.^[53,79,221–223] The results of refs. [53,222] showed good agreement with experimental findings.

Segregation of solute atoms to extended defects, particularly GBs in HEAs and MEAs, can influence their mechanical

properties and thermal stability.^[230–234] This segregation can be induced by annealing or irradiation.^[235–237] Annealing-induced segregation can be simulated using hybrid MC/MD methods at GBs.^[231,234,238,239] Irradiation-induced segregation at GBs can also occur in HEAs and MEAs.^[236,237] As such, segregation has been identified as a key microstructural feature governing irradiation-assisted stress corrosion cracking and localized intergranular corrosion resistance in conventional alloys like Fe–Ni–Cr austenitic steels;^[240] it is crucial to consider this phenomenon when designing novel HEAs and MEAs for radiation applications. Displacement cascade simulations using MD can elucidate the relationship between GB properties (e.g., excess energy, excess volume, and defect segregation energy) and the characteristics of irradiation damage in HEAs and MEAs.^[226,227,241] Molecular statics (MS) calculations can also provide insights into the migration and formation energies of defects near GBs in HEAs.^[242,243]

As discussed earlier, CSRO can influence the mechanical properties of these alloys. CSRO has also been demonstrated to impact the radiation response of M/HEAs.^[203,244,245] Zhang et al. revealed through MD displacement cascade simulations that CSRO can delay the initiation of damage in equimolar CoNiCr.^[244] Using cascade overlap simulations, Zhou et al. showed that CSRO can be destructed after several dpa.^[245] Additionally, using kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) simulations, they demonstrated that CSRO recovery is another event that can occur when both irradiation and temperature effects are considered in the equiatomic NiCoFeCrMn HEA^[245] Experimentally, Su et al. observed that CSRO in equiatomic NiCoFeCrMn can be tuned by irradiation at high temperatures.^[246] Furthermore, Arkoub et al.,^[203] utilizing cascade overlap MD simulations, found that the reduced defect diffusivity induced by CSRO in FeNiCr MEA

can lead to the aggregation of specific elements near interstitial dislocation loops.

There are few interatomic potentials available to describe helium interactions with the metallic elements of HEAs. Recently, Xiong et al. developed such an interatomic potential.^[68] They utilized MD and MS simulations to study the behavior of refractory MPEAs—specifically WTaTi, WTaCrV, and WTaCrVTi—under helium implantation and compared the results with pure W. Their findings revealed that the distribution of implanted helium in MPEAs is only minimally influenced by surface orientation. Furthermore, helium bubbles in MPEAs were significantly smaller and more discretely located compared to those in pure W. These results indicate that MPEAs exhibit superior resistance to surface modifications from energetic helium ions, highlighting their potential as promising materials for nuclear reactors.

The above discussion highlights that despite the limitations of MD, and considering the multiscale nature of radiation damage, MD simulations, especially with accurate interatomic potentials, can provide valuable insights for designing radiation-resistant materials. This subsection reviewed recent studies on the radiation response of HEAs and MEAs using MD and MS with CIPs. The next subsection will discuss how MD simulations with MLIPs can describe radiation damage and defect behavior.

5.1.2. Radiation Damage in M/HEAs: MD Simulations Using MLIPs

The accuracy of MD simulations is highly dependent on the precision of the interatomic potential. Recently, significant efforts have been made to develop MLIP to achieve accuracy comparable to DFT for irradiation applications.

DL-based interatomic potentials are a class of MLIPs that, by training on a dataset of physical and defect properties, can be used to simulate radiation damage in metals and alloys more accurately than CIPs.^[247–251] The DeePMD-kit software package can be used to train the DP interatomic potential.^[252] In displacement cascade simulations, atoms can come very close due to short-distance collisions. To model such interactions, the interatomic potentials are smoothly connected to short-range Ziegler–Biersack–Littmark (ZBL) repulsive interactions.^[253] Wang et al. integrated the ZBL potential into a DP energy model (ZBL-DP) to accurately describe short atomic distances during irradiation.^[247] This model was used to simulate irradiation damage in FCC aluminum, providing reliable predictions for defect formation energy, collision cascade evolution, displacement threshold energy, and residual point defects compared to traditional ZBL-CIPs.^[247] In addition, the ZBL-DP MLIP has been developed to investigate radiation damage in ϵ -ZrH and W.^[248,249] The ZBL-DP MLIP for tungsten is reliable for investigating elasticity-related properties in irradiated tungsten.^[249] Wang et al. also developed a DP MLIP for W-H, demonstrating that it accurately describes the basic properties of bcc tungsten, the behavior of solute hydrogen, hydrogen adsorption and migration on tungsten surfaces, interactions between hydrogen atoms and vacancies, dislocations, and neighboring interstitial hydrogen atoms, and the formation energy of hydrogen self-clusters, matching the accuracy of ab initio calculations.^[250] Pitike et al. developed

a DP MLIP for Fe–He to investigate helium bubble accumulation in Fe.^[251] This potential calculates binding energies in $V_{m,vac}He_n$ bubbles and He_n clusters with a mean absolute error (MAE) of just 70 meV, significantly lower than the MAE of binding energies estimated using empirical potentials. Despite the application of DP interatomic potentials in predicting properties of M/HEAs,^[254–257] their use in studying irradiation properties of these materials remains unexplored.

The GAP is another accurate MLIP that was recently extended to include the description of radiation effects.^[258,259] A faster version of GAP, known as tabulated GAP, has been developed to increase the efficiency for displacement cascade simulation.^[85,90,259,260] Koskenniemi et al. investigated primary radiation damage in W and an equimolar binary W–Mo alloy using GAP and tabGAP MLIP potentials.^[259] They demonstrated that tabGAP is two orders of magnitude faster than GAP while producing comparable defect numbers and cluster sizes. Additionally, they found that W–Mo exhibits similar numbers of surviving defects as pure W, with more efficient defect recombination both during and after cascades.^[259] Wei et al. studied the primary radiation damage in W_xTa_{1-x} and W_xMo_{1-x} alloys using tab-GAP and classical embedded atom method (EAM) potentials for various cascade energies.^[260] Both potentials showed similar trends in the number of surviving defects for W_xMo_{1-x} alloys as a function of x , with tabGAP predicting fewer defects overall. In contrast, the number of surviving defects for W_xTa_{1-x} alloys showed different trends between the two potentials, which were explained by variations in threshold displacement energies (TDE) and melting temperatures.^[260] Recently, the tab-GAP MLIP has been used to investigate radiation damage in Mo–Nb–Ta–V–W RHEA using MD simulations.^[90] This study examined radiation damage accumulation up to 0.4–0.8 dpa, followed by high-temperature annealing, in pure W, W-based equiatomic binaries, ternaries, quaternaries, and the quinary HEAs. The results indicated that V-containing alloys exhibit low swelling and exceptionally efficient defect annealing compared to pure W and V-free alloys.^[90] Fellman et al. recently developed a tab-GAP interatomic potential for the AlCrCuFeNi HEA system to investigate radiation damage in $Al_xCrCuFeNi_y$ compositions.^[85] Their overlapping cascade simulations revealed a strong dependence on aluminum content in terms of defect accumulation. In general, alloys with higher Al content exhibited greater defect concentrations. Interestingly, the study also reported the formation of CSRO during continued irradiation.^[85]

MTP is another MLIP that can describe interactions in metallic systems. Based on our recent review, this type of potential has been developed for Nb, Ti, Fe, FeAl, TiAl, Zr, Zr–Sn, CoNiFe, NbMoTaW, MoNbTaTiW, TaVCrW, TiZrHfTa, and VNbMoTaW metallic systems.^[115,120,123,130–134,261–266] Among these, only the bcc-iron MTP MLIP has been developed to investigate collision cascades.^[262] This potential can accurately reproduce short-range repulsive interactions, GSFE, dislocation core structures, and the formation energies of defect clusters.^[262] An MTP MLIP developed for the NbMoTaW RHEA^[130] is widely used to study CSRO and the segregation of atoms at GBs using hybrid MC/MD in this HEA.^[267–270] Greigor et al. conducted an extensive study of segregation at GBs in the NbMoTaW RHEA using hybrid MC/MD simulations and MTP on hundreds of bicrystals along the [001] symmetric tilt axis.^[269] Their analysis

covered over 130 000 GB sites, each with unique local atomic environments. This comprehensive approach illuminated the complex relationship between local GB structure and CSRO. Using a ML framework, they implemented several models to isolate the contributions of structural and chemical driving forces on segregation behavior. The prediction of Mo segregation showed the most improvement when both structural and chemical descriptors were used as input parameters.^[269] Askey et al. demonstrated how grain size, temperature, and crystallographic orientation modify segregation both at and near the interfacial regions using hybrid MC/MD simulations and MTP in the NbMoTaW RHEA.^[270] In their recent work, Aksoy et al. developed a ML framework to predict GB segregation in complex alloys like NbMoTaW RHEA.^[268] Their approach integrates atomistic simulations using MTP MLIP with ML, producing a large dataset and an efficient NN. They claim that this robust and adaptable tool allows for high-throughput investigations into cosegregation behavior in other M/HEAs, reducing the need for expensive atomistic simulations.^[268]

SNAP MLIP has been developed to describe metallic systems such as Al, Mo, Ta, W, W-H, W-ZrC, Mo-Re, Ni-Mo, NbMoTaW, and MoNbTaTi.^[135,271–279] The SNAP potentials that have been used to investigate radiation damage and defect properties include W, Mo, W-H, and NbMoTaW RHEA.^[272,273,275,280] Warrier et al. compared the primary radiation damage in W in the range of 5–150 keV PKA energy for several different interatomic potentials.^[273] It has been shown that $\langle 111 \rangle$ clusters dominate across all interatomic potentials, except for the SNAP potential. The SNAP potential shows a significantly higher

number of C15-like rings across all PKA energies.^[273] Additionally, the SNAP potential indicates a higher fraction of in-cluster vacancies.^[273] Hydrogen self-clustering was investigated by performing MD simulations at different temperatures using the W-H SNAP MLIP.^[275] For HEAs, Li et al. developed a SNAP MLIP for the NbMoTaW alloy.^[135] Their research demonstrated that thermodynamically driven segregation of Nb to the GBs and enrichment of W within the grains enhance the observed CSRO.^[135] By using this SNAP potential, a recent study investigated the properties of self-interstitial atoms (SIAs) in the NbMoTaW RHEA.^[280] The formation and migration energies, as well as the diffusion properties of SIAs in this alloy, were analyzed. The findings revealed that the $\langle 111 \rangle$ orientation is the most common among all configurations, with a notable occurrence of octahedral SIAs also observed. In terms of diffusivity, the study identified two distinct regimes below and above 600 K, where SIA diffusion transitions from 1D to 3D.^[280] A SNAP MLIP for HEAs was recently developed for the MoNbTaTi alloy.^[279] The CSRO and its effect on vacancy formation energy were investigated.^[279] The results demonstrated that Mo and Ta strongly favor each other as neighbors and can form B2 phases. The CSRO in the MoNbTaTi HEA severely affects the vacancy formation energy.^[279]

One of the key advantages of MLIPs is their ability to study a much larger set of configurations than DFT, which is particularly important in HEAs where the local environments of point defects are complex, and the formation energies of point defects depend strongly on these local environments. In **Figure 10**, the formation energies of 1726 dumbbell configurations computed

Figure 10. Distribution of formation energies for various dumbbell configurations calculated using a MLIP^[144] for the disordered equiatomic Ta-Ti-V-W alloy with 432 atomic sites. Each series corresponds to a different atomic pair in the dumbbell, with the first element indicating one atom and the second indicating the other (e.g., “TiV” represents a dumbbell with one Ti and one V atom). The dumbbell configurations are arranged with increasing sum of their atomic radius.

using MLIP from ref. [144] for a disordered equiatomic Ta–Ti–V–W alloy are presented. The results show that dumbbells containing V and Ti atoms, which have smaller atomic radii, exhibit lower mean formation energies, whereas those involving Ta and W, which have larger atomic radii, display higher values. Mixed dumbbells follow similar trends, for example, with V–Ti configurations displaying significantly lower formation energies than V–Ta or V–W dumbbells.

5.1.3. Defect Behavior in M/HEAs: kMC and ML Approaches

The rough potential energy landscape (PEL) of M/HEAs leads to more complex diffusion behavior of defects in these alloys. kMC is a powerful method for simulating the time evolution of defect structures in metals and alloys, especially when the timescale of MD simulations cannot be reached. In kMC, the system is characterized by a set of possible events, each with a specific rate. For defect diffusion, the rate of a migration event is often determined by its migration energy barriers (ΔE_{ij}) for possible migration paths to nearest neighbor sites and the temperature, typically using an Arrhenius-type equation^[281,28]

$$R_{ij} = \nu_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_{ij}}{k_B T}\right) \quad (4)$$

where R_{ij} is the jump frequency, ν_0 is the attempt frequency (or prefactor), k_B is Boltzmann's constant, and T is the temperature. The total migration rate is calculated as

$$R_{\text{tot}} = \sum_j R_{ij} \quad (5)$$

By generating a random number $r_1 \in (0, 1]$ and using cumulative probability, the migration path j_k can be determined

$$\sum_{j=1}^{j_k-1} R_{ij} \leq r_1 R_{\text{tot}} < \sum_{j=1}^{j_k} R_{ij} \quad (6)$$

The simulation time is then updated by

$$\Delta t = -\frac{1}{R_{\text{tot}}} \ln(r_2) \quad (7)$$

where r_2 is another random number.

Calculating the migration barrier in the rough PEL of random or partially ordered M/HEAs is challenging. Generally, the vacancy migration barrier can be calculated using the nudged elastic band (NEB)^[283] method in DFT or classical MD codes, such as LAMMPS. However, covering the migration barrier for the entire local environment is difficult. In this case, a NN can be trained using a migration barrier dataset from DFT/LAMMPS to predict it for any local environment. By combining NN with kMC, the diffusion of vacancies—which plays an important role in the evolution of defects in irradiated samples—can be investigated in the complex environments of M/HEAs. Below, you can find recent studies on this topic.

Fan et al.^[284] used LAMMPS and MLIP to generate a dataset of migration barriers for random and CSRO configurations in MoNbTa MEAs. They then demonstrated the use of cutting-edge DL technology—convolutional NNs (CNN)—to predict spectra of

path-dependent vacancy migration energy barriers. In another study, a dataset of migration barriers for $\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x$ ($x = 0-1$) FCC alloys was created using the NEB method in LAMMPS.^[285] They developed an ANN based ML model to accurately predict vacancy migration barriers for various local atomic environments. This ANN model was coupled with kMC (ANN-kMC) simulations to determine vacancy migration barriers on-the-fly, enabling efficient studies of vacancy diffusion across the entire composition range and a broad temperature range.^[285] The high-throughput ANN-kMC method was also used to study the diffusion behavior in 1500 nonequiatomic FeNiCrCoCu HEA compositions.^[285] The dataset for training the ANN was created by using NEB and EAM potentials in LAMMPS. It was discovered that sluggish diffusion, though absent in equiatomic HEA, occurs in many nonequiatomic compositions.^[285] In a related effort, ML models were developed to accurately represent the local atomic environment dependence of the PEL in HEAs.^[282] By combining the ML model with the kMC method, the study revealed that self-diffusion in HEAs is predominantly governed by the PEL roughness, characterized by elemental-specific site energies and migration barriers.^[282] These methods were used for different alloy systems, specifically examining the binary system $\text{Fe}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}$ and the ternary system $\text{Fe}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{Cr}_{1-x-y}$. LAMMPS was used to generate the training dataset of migration energy barriers.^[282] In recent studies, Xing et al.^[286,287] focused on diffusion in MoNbTa MEAs by developing NN kinetics (NNK). They examined the temperature-dependent local chemical ordering in a refractory NbMoTa MEA, identifying a critical temperature at which the B2 order phase reaches a maximum.^[287] Utilizing NNK, they investigated vacancy diffusion in the NbMoTa alloy across a broad temperature range (2600–800 K).^[286] Unlike pure metals, the diffusion correlation factor (f) and activation energy (ΔG_m), which are key parameters for diffusion, are not constant in alloys and decrease considerably as temperature decreases.^[286] Manzoor et al.^[288] studied the interplay between thermal vacancies and CSRO in equimolar NiCoCr alloy using high-throughput atomic calculations, finding that CSRO reduces equilibrium vacancy concentration and diffusivity. They developed a framework combining a ML model, lattice kinetic Monte Carlo (LKMC), and thermodynamic theory to predict these effects. Their ML model, trained on atomistic data, accurately predicts vacancy formation energy and migration barriers for ordered and disordered local environments.^[288] Xu et al. developed a ML-kMC method to investigate the connection between percolation and diffusion characteristics in CoCrNi MEAs.^[289] Their findings revealed that the occurrence of site percolation does not necessarily lead to sluggish diffusion in MEAs.^[289] Instead, the impact of percolation on diffusion is significantly influenced by the distribution of energy barriers among the different constituent species, which in turn affects the correlation factor and jump frequency.

5.2. ML for Predicting Radiation Response from Experimental Data

Various irradiation effects can be detected via different experimental methods depending on the type of irradiation effect. Irradiation-induced mechanical property changes can be

revealed via experimental methods such as hardness tests, tensile tests, and impact tests. Irradiation-induced nano/microstructural changes can be divulged through microscopy and spectroscopy experiments based on electron and X-ray sources.

For instance, **Figure 11** shows the effects of 3 MeV Ni²⁺ ion irradiation at 580 °C up to a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ on the single-crystal NiCoFe MEA. Figure 11a illustrates a nanoindentation hardness chart obtained via the nanoindentation technique, demonstrating an increase in hardness of the NiCoFe MEA with irradiation by about 25%. This irradiation-induced hardening is a manifestation of the presence of defect structures induced by irradiation and their response to stimuli. For example, Figure 11b shows a scanning TEM-BF image indicating the presence of large dislocation microstructures (red arrows) in the irradiated region of the same NiCoFe MEA sample, representing the microstructural origins of the irradiation hardening.

ML methods have been utilizing such experimental data sets to predict irradiation-induced phenomena in structural materials, which are usually detrimental to their application in nuclear reactors. Some of the ML-based studies primarily focused on reactor pressure vessel (RPV) steels for irradiation embrittlement.^[143,290–293] Cottrell et al. used a Bayesian-based NN model to predict the changes in ductile to brittle transition temperature (DBTT) in low-activation martensitic steel.^[290] The model described irradiation temperature as the most significant factor as the changes in DBTT decrease with increasing irradiation temperature and the effect saturates at irradiation temperature greater than 450 °C.^[290] Bing et al. used a DNN to establish the relation between alloy composition, neutron flux, and irradiation embrittlement of RPV steels. The model demonstrated that at a given neutron fluence, irradiation embrittlement is more evident at lower neutron flux.^[291] The work described the effect of Cu, P, and Ni elements on the change in DBTT and should be maintained very low. The study also showed that the synergy of Cu and Ni influences irradiation embrittlement more than Cu and Mn.^[291] Liu et al. applied the Gaussian Kernel Ridge Regression ML method and successfully predicted the temperature, composition, fluence, and flux dependence on the irradiation hardening of RPV steels using the data from test reactors

IVAR T16, BR2, and ATR-2.^[292] The model also revealed the composition and fluence dependence on the flux. The work is consistent with physics-based rate-theory models such as EONY and OWAY.^[292] Xu et al. predicted irradiation-induced transition temperature shifts (TTS) based on irradiation embrittlement data for RPV steels using the XGBoost method.^[293] The work collected irradiation embrittlement data of SA508-3 and 16MND5 containing subjects such as neutron fluence, irradiation temperature, irradiation flux, chemical composition (Cu, P, Mn, Ni, Si, etc.), material type, and TTS. The model predicted that TTS is not affected for $\text{Cu} \leq 0.07\%$ and $\text{Cu} \geq 0.26\%$ and increases gradually with Cu content otherwise. The model also envisaged that TTS decreases with irradiation temperature, increases with fluence, and is not affected by flux changes significantly. All the predictions of this high-accuracy model are consistent with the existing irradiation embrittlement physical mechanisms.^[293]

Bing et al. used a DNN with back propagation to establish the relation between alloy composition, neutron irradiation dose and temperature, and irradiation swelling of austenitic stainless steels.^[294] The model demonstrated that Ti and Si reduce and Ni amplify irradiation swelling. Also, the study showed that Cr, Ni, Cr, and Ti increase the dose of swelling inflection point, while C and P reduce the swelling inflection point dose.^[294]

Identification and characterization of crystallographic defects are paramount in irradiated materials, as these defects lead to the degradation of physical and mechanical properties. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is one of the experimental techniques that captures irradiation-induced defects such as dislocations (red arrows in Figure 11b), stacking fault tetrahedrons (SFTs), and cavities. Automatic identification of such nanometer scale defects from the TEM images via computer vision can be taxing owing to the complicated contrast mechanisms. Moreover, defects induced by focused ion beams (red circles in Figure 11b) during the preparation of TEM samples could also intervene in the analysis of irradiation-induced defects. Hence, ML methods have been applied recently to probe irradiation-induced defects from TEM data sets.^[295–297] Burns et al. developed an end-to-end process of analyzing time series

Figure 11. Examples of irradiation effects captured via experiments. a) Nanoindentation hardness chart showing an increase in the hardness post-irradiation for single-crystal NiCoFe MEA, indicating irradiation hardening. b) Scanning TEM-bright field image of single-crystal NiCoFe MEA showing dislocation structures in the irradiated region indicated by red arrows for example. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).^[63] Copyright 2024, The Authors, published by SSRN.

micrographs obtained from in-situ irradiation TEM for Cu. The study used a CNN to assess the defect generation rate, defect cluster density, and saturation of defects and successfully identified phenomena such as coalescence and fragmentation.^[295] The work used TEM data sets collected via the two-beam conditions technique with over 200 000 defects, which were hand-labeled to establish the ground truth data for the ML method. The workflow of the ML method first consisted of data normalization followed by data training using U Net++ architecture. The test data was then processed to obtain probability maps and later converted to binary masks via thresholding, which were subsequently treated to separate the touching and overlapping defects and label unique objects. Finally, the defect borders were recognized via contour detection, and the sizes and shapes of the features were measured. The work identified defect numbers similar to the ground truth data sets. Thus, the method delivers rapid results with good accuracy for characterizing defects induced by irradiation in FCC metals such as Cu and Pd. However, the study did not separate the defect types, such as the dislocation loops and SFTs, in the micrographs.^[295]

Roberts et al. built a hybrid CNN algorithm, DefectSegNet, to segment irradiation defects using neutron-irradiated HT9 martensitic steel as a model alloy.^[296] The authors used diffraction-contrast scanning TEM-BF imaging to identify three defects, dislocations, precipitates, and voids, to reduce multiple contrast mechanisms associated with conventional TEM and provide monotonic contrast free of artifacts and bend contours. The STEM images were preprocessed to enhance the defect contrast further and later hand-labeled to obtain the ground truth data. The authors then carried out image augmentation to minimize the risk of over-fitting by including rotated and horizontally flipped images into the training data subsets. The authors developed a hybrid deep-learning CNN method, DefectSegNet, which provided the best performance for dislocations. The dislocation density calculations by the model exhibited only a meagre error of up to 5% compared to ground truth densities. The studies also compared the ML results with the results obtained from human experts. In the case of precipitate density and size calculations, DefectSegNet achieved 10% and 2% errors, respectively, while the human error was around 45% and 13%. However, the method underperformed for void density and size calculations due to the overlap of voids and precipitates. Sainju et al. designed a DL-based multiobject tracking model, DefectTrack, to track Kr ion-irradiation-induced defect clusters in Ni from the videos obtained via in-situ TEM.^[297]

The current section explains the ML methods applied for the prediction of irradiation effects, such as irradiation embrittlement and irradiation swelling, from the available experimental data sets and for classification and quantification of irradiation-induced defects from the TEM image data sets. The ML methods have been demonstrated mainly on steel materials such as RPV steels, austenitic stainless steels, and martensitic stainless steels. Hence, there is ample scope for the exploration and application of ML methods for predicting the behavior of MEAs and HEAs upon irradiation. However, the availability of experimental data sets for novel materials such as MEAs and HEAs is scarce. Therefore, there is a need for conducting high-throughput irradiation experiments at varied conditions of flux, fluence, and temperature for multiple M/HEAs. Such experiments would

generate data sets to train ML methods for the prediction of unique M/HEA compositions with superior irradiation damage resistance. However, such experiments are difficult to conduct under neutron irradiation conditions owing to the cost, time, and safety regulations involved. Hence, surrogate irradiation techniques such as ion irradiation must be explored. Such facilities and efforts have been under consideration recently, and the preliminary research results have been promising.^[70,298] Moorehead et al. successfully demonstrated such experiments and generated data sets for multiple compositions in the composition space of Cr–Mn–Fe–Ni via additive manufacturing, ion-irradiation, and characterization techniques such as nanoindentation, X-ray fluorescence, X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, and energy-dispersive spectroscopy.^[70,298] In this context, more data sets could be generated and ML scientists should see this as a huge opportunity to predict irradiation effects in M/HEAs.

6. Summary

In this review, we have undertaken an effort to look HEA systems from the viewpoint of materials under irradiation. Due to the complexity of the materials and the typical scenarios in which they are studied and would be eventually used, using ML approaches would seem to bring an extra tool to expedite research and bring complex alloys to the forefront. The quintessential problems with nuclear materials are the slowness of the research cycle due to the need to test candidate systems under close-to-reality irradiation environments and the need to meet stringent industry requirements down the road. Several national and international efforts try to tackle this challenge, partly or as a whole, often exploiting advances in material informatics and ICME. How this picture will play out in the reality of nuclear materials research as regards HEAs is something we next consider with a concrete example of research being planned and conducted in Europe at the time of writing this overview.

6.1. Example: ConnectNM—Advancing Nuclear Materials Research with ML

6.1.1. Ambition and Objective

CONNECT-NM, the initiative funded through the Euratom Research and Training Programme (EURATOM) under the call HORIZON-EURATOM-2023-NRT-01, is at the forefront of advancing nuclear materials research by leveraging cutting-edge digital techniques, particularly ML. In a field where safety and sustainability are paramount, CONNECT-NM will aim to innovate materials designed to operate under extreme conditions, such as high temperatures, high irradiation doses, and chemically aggressive environments. This initiative specifically will explore the potential of HEAs, known for their exceptional strength and resistance to corrosion, alongside traditional materials to meet these challenges. The overall ambition of CONNECT-NM is to foster a paradigm shift in nuclear materials research, moving from the traditional “observe and qualify” approach to a modern “design and control” methodology. This shift will be enabled by the coordinated exploitation of national competencies, facilities,

Figure 12. Main research lines and expected final product in CONNECT-NM, according to the official website of CONNECT-NM (<https://www.connect-nm.eu/about/#Objectives>).

and infrastructures across Europe, bringing together entities with a national mandate for nuclear materials research. The main research lines and the expected final product of this project are presented in **Figure 12**. Lines 1 and 5 concern in particular data and the use of ML in the context of nuclear materials. Apart from ML, CONNECT-NM will embrace also other modern digital techniques, including data analytics, high-performance computing, and robotics, which are central to data-driven modeling, high-throughput experiments, and the development of digital twins.

6.1.2. Tools and Techniques

To achieve its goals, CONNECT-NM will use a variety of advanced tools. Central to this is data-driven modeling, where ML is used to analyze and classify data, identify correlations between material properties of HEAs, and iteratively select the best candidates for specific applications. This will be further enhanced by high-performance computing, allowing for complex and accurate simulations that blend advanced physical models with data-driven approaches. Another critical tool is the digital twin—virtual representations of real systems, including materials and components, that are continuously updated with data throughout their lifecycle. Digital twins integrate various modeling approaches, from empirical to data-driven, to ensure precise simulations that can predict material behavior in real-world conditions. This integration is crucial for optimizing the performance of HEAs and ensuring safety across the entire lifecycle of nuclear components.

6.1.3. Actions

CONNECT-NM is aiming to implement several key initiatives leveraging, in particular, ML and other advanced digital techniques in nuclear materials research. In the area of nondestructive examination and material health monitoring, the initiative is developing digital twins that combine aging models with data-driven techniques to enhance diagnostics and prognostics of materials. These digital twins are continuously updated via

sensor measurements, providing real-time insights into material conditions. Additionally, CONNECT-NM is advancing the back-training of models using inspection data, improving the understanding of materials properties throughout the product lifecycle. This approach enables the identification of defect origins with significant prior knowledge. In the field of advanced materials (HEAs) modeling and characterization, CONNECT-NM is pushing the boundaries of data-driven models. By using ML to extract relevant features from large datasets, the initiative is addressing the limitations of physical models and improving the prediction of material behaviors under extreme conditions, including the resilience of HEAs to radiation-induced damage.

6.2. Forward Look

Finally, the main split one may apply in the context of this review is between ML methods as applied in materials science in general for HEAs and those that are particularly relevant for these alloys under irradiation. We do not attempt a general overview of the vast field of ML for materials from which progress is expected and is also being made for the sake of HEAs, but instead follow this division by first summarizing the main directions of ML in materials and then making some pertinent comments on HEAs under irradiation.

The general use of ML methods in the area of metal alloys typically involves classifying data and predicting new alloy compositions from data sets.^[98] In the case of HEAs, this becomes more complex due to the extremely intricate phase diagrams and the formation of secondary structures, which provide thermodynamic pathways for creating, for example, Laves phases or precipitates—structures that may be of interest for irradiation resistance or mechanical properties. Of particular interest is the use of brute-force DL approaches, including generative ML, to generate surrogate data and candidate alloys using adversarial methods. A notable development in general materials informatics is the use of DL for classification and feature detection in microscopy (TEM^[299,300] and sometimes SEM as

a function of time) due to the difficulty of interpreting image data.^[98] For HEAs under irradiation, this becomes particularly interesting due to the local disorder, often-present CSRO, dislocations, and irradiation damage occurring on various scales. These effects, of course, may be highly system- and irradiation-specific.

Lastly, we address the role of ML in developing new workflows for simulations, both through the construction of surrogate models from datasets and, in particular, by simplifying material simulations through the substitution of more complex, fundamental approaches such as DFT. In this context, the landscape of HEAs under irradiation will benefit from the introduction of novel tools, especially with regard to ML potentials. A topic worth mentioning is the use of LLMs in materials science. The current trend in the use of LLMs is either to pose domain-specific questions using the LLM and available data or to construct complete workflows by creating a hierarchy of models and processes.^[160] In spite of its promise, this approach, in our view, lies beyond the scope of relevance to the current topic in the near future.

To summarize the main points about the use of ML for HEAs under irradiation conditions, we concentrate on the challenges that seem to be more relevant at the moment. As discussed in the previous subsection, there has been slower-than-expected progress in securing large-scale funding for the field, including for HEA research. This ranges from data management and curation—a critical starting point for ML applications—to so-called Materials Acceleration Platforms. However, for the sake of scientific generality, we now highlight a few relevant points. 1) HEA and irradiation—the main question is whether enough data exist—to be exploited with ML—that show how these alloys respond to irradiation, whether in Gen IV or V fission reactor structural components or, for instance, advanced coatings. A specific problem is the phase prediction of HEAs at a certain temperature as a function of composition, under irradiation. ML methods have recently been enlisted to this end,^[43,157,301] but radiation effects are not much included due to the lack of data. It might be possible (see point 3) below) to circumvent the lack of experimental data using trustworthy damage simulations to create surrogate data (like in ref. [301] does using GAN-type approach in a similar case of an original data set lacking power.)” 2) The use of “small-data” methods of the Bayesian or GPR breed^[98] enables researchers to generate the data “on the fly.”^[302] The generic advantages of these ML ideas include probabilistic estimates of data and prediction uncertainties, the easiness for Pareto Optimal solutions for multitarget optimization, and bounded data spaces (e.g., in compositional space). The use of this approach is easy to foresee in the context of purely modeling research, but it should be used to accelerate testing HEAs under irradiation campaigns due to their time-consuming complexity. The natural idea for this is “batch” BO where the experimental design is done step by step. 3) The main promise of ML-based simulations for HEAs lies in the ease of generating interatomic potentials for use in MD simulations. In this context, a key question is whether these methods can be extended to reliably reproduce irradiation damage, the dynamics of resulting defects, and their temporal evolution, particularly at elevated temperatures, where phase stability becomes a complicating factor. Consequently, one would also expect these methods to faithfully reproduce other key properties such as elastic modulus,

yield stress, and the physics at surfaces, important for corrosion. Of particular importance is the potential formation of CSRO due to irradiation,^[85,88] which can significantly influence all relevant material properties. This research area remains highly challenging due to the vast HEAs compositional space. Modeling results should be benchmarked against experimental data, calling for systematic approaches in which theoretical models are first validated using simpler binary and ternary alloys.

6.3. Final Summary and Future Directions

The topic of this review combines two materials science issues, HEAs and their behavior in irradiation environments, ML as a toolbox, and, as a future prospect, the exploitation of HEAs in nuclear environments. A critical distinction in this context lies in the origin of the data to be studied or generated: whether experimental or simulation-based.

In this regard, one hopes for synergy between atomistic simulations and ML analysis of experimental data in providing comprehensive insights into the radiation response of HEAs. One expects that the use of surrogate data in combination with more costly and slow experiments may offer ways of developing novel, usable HEA materials. One may identify key challenges in modeling and predicting the radiation response of HEAs, which parallel the usual paradigm of ML in materials science, including data scarcity and model transferability. One development that will certainly prove to be of use is the concept of “small data,” in contrast to the usual idea that the use of ML methods requires big data. Bayesian and other methods work with smaller datasets and provide tools for parameter or property space exploration with probabilistic estimates of the uncertainties. They also provide approaches for material design and optimization, including multiobjective design problems. Pareto-optimal solutions, i.e., in the context of compositional landscape searches for alloys offering several optimized properties are an exciting future route in spite of the complexity of such problems.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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